

Nothing is as seriously important as playing, not just in IT.

Gaming trends

By THOMAS HOBERG

As with children, the future of information technology depends on the quality of its playing: this lies in experimentation, which is at the heart of engineering and science.

Key insights

- Computer gaming with its huge user base and unlimited appetite for realism has become the most important driver for innovation in information technology.
- Games push every frontier: increased realism, larger worlds, bigger crowds, lower cost, greater network bandwidth and lower network latencies.
- Planet-sized distributed game worlds enable critical global digital twins for virtual personal assistants (VPA).
- The battle of digital distribution platforms calls for regulation, splitting roles to avoid straggling consumers.

Key recommendations

- Take gaming seriously: it is the main motor of innovation in every field of IT.
- Support serious applications for gaming technology: autonomous vehicles and machinery as well as virtual personal assistants require digital twins in an open world game at planet size.
- Ensure the EU have as full a set of IP assets for game technology as possible: treat it as critical infrastructure and encourage the development of open source components to enable heterogenous open worlds.
- Regulate to separate gaming platforms, separate game studios, stores, servers and draw ground geography borders into the clouds to avoid monopolization and ensure consumers won't lose access to purchased games or are forced into subscriptions.
- Regulate that purchased game titles can be freely moved between platforms and devices and that behind a 'buy' button is a real purchase.

Gaming at the core of IT evolution

Without acting out our ingrained playfulness we could not make sense of our senses, nor articulate our limbs let alone a thought. Life is a constant dance in our brain, what we sense, what we do, and how that changes our perception. When kittens play "catch-a-tail" or babies "grab-taste-drop" they develop the most important skills required for long-term survival through systematic experimentation and training. The world is really a game in our head, reality what we share with those we choose to believe, parents or peers, charlatans or scientists.

Experimentation with careful analysis and abstraction allowed engineers and scientists to develop models that lend themselves to extrapolation and recombination, so results could be projected: not

every bridge or cathedral had to be fully tested before the final construction, once the statics and materials were understood. From the very beginning, computers have been used to fill the gaps between experiments and project the properties of experiments now executed much quicker as simulations. In fact, computer chips themselves are among the most complex structures, constructed and simulated in code-only for most of their design, aiming for immediate usability of the first production run. Such pure digital design, where most if not all design stages are made on computers, became possible mostly because of a virtuous circle so typical in information technology:

- Computers became cheap enough to experiment and play with;
- Some of these games were inspiring enough to increase the user base;

- The additional user base paid for an improved implementation;
- Improved implementations found professional applications.

The first hobby computer flight simulator from 1980 on the Apple II computer

Figure 1: Early version of the flight simulator. (Source: https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/en/5/5f/Sublogic_Flight_Simulator_II.png)

offered little more than the main dials of an aircraft and an extremely rough sketch of major landmarks and the landing strips as coloured dots on 280x192 pixels, but the moving contours provided a seasoned flyer or passenger with enough visual cues to imagine moving through the air in a plane. The 1 MHz 8-Bit CPU not only had to manage a physical model of an aircraft and the effect of its control surfaces on the flight path, but it had to project a vector representation of the terrain onto the bitmap display and draw each resulting pixel. The human mind did most of the work of interpolation and imagination into a glide path, which worked incredibly well and it is hard to exaggerate the inspirational effect it and its successors had on the computer industry.

Good looking vs. looking good enough, another uncanny valley

Early games resemble stories and books where the listener was responsible for translating a description of a scene into an image in the mind. Realism had to be limited to what computers could support and users could afford; real-time response was much more important. Comic-like two-dimensional side scrolling games gained colour, detail and resolution, but 3D solutions targeted the professional market, where very boring surfaces with flat colours might actually be preferred in CAD.

A quantum jump in game quality was achieved in 1995 when texture mapping accelerators became affordable, which would project an image bitmap on an otherwise rather flat polygon mesh composed of triangles. Ironically this happened just after *Wolfenstein*, *Doom* and *Quake* from ID-Software had popularized 3D games which had been extensively optimized to run with software-only rendering. Since it could be performed for every triangle in an embarrassingly parallel manner without interdependence, dedicated hardware could perform this much faster than any CPU via iteration, even if those raced from 60-3800MHz in the ten years that followed. It enabled a new species of games with a third dimension, mazes and worlds much easier to get lost in and hooked on.

A naturalistic rendering of a real scene would require not only infinitesimal detail in data and model, it also requires tracing the path of each ray of light as it reflects, scatters or is finally absorbed. It explodes in complexity with image resolution and dynamic range and puts a linear dependency on each ray with a variable number of iterations breaking the latency requirements of games. It became the preferred path for digital art and computer generated films, which could much less afford to sacrifice image quality and therefore run

their final renders for weeks or months on giant computer farms for an hour of video.

For many iterations of graphic processing units (GPUs), the only path to better-looking graphics was to improve the cheating around the processing of textures from a fixed function process to something more adaptive. For example, instead of breaking up larger triangles into smaller ones to create finer contours, bump maps were introduced, which add a z-axis offset much like colour to a texture to create dents and elevations, or add logic to fuzzy or sharpen edges and texture details to avoid edge and texture flicker as surfaces moved much closer or further away. It ultimately led to an architecture that used code routines to do all the texture processing instead of fixed function ASIC blocks and thus gave birth to today's GPUs, which are fully programmable and have transformed HPC and machine learning. They have even picked up some limited ray tracing functionality recently and became flexible enough to accelerate digital film rendering, but nowhere near real-time frame rates. It is a bit like zooming in on a Mandelbrot set: the computational gap between fidelity and frame rates only seems to increase, the closer you get.

Something similar is now happening with the simulation model behind the scenes.

Most of the early 3D games were quite literally set in stone. Stone walls helped to limit the computational cost of visual depth while their immutable nature allowed eliminating many inside surfaces and polygons. It also made for minimal communication bandwidth requirements for multi-player games, as a static world would not alter, only dynamic object and player information needed to be exchanged. Even today creating the most realistic looking maps, objects and characters requires artistic design and manual optimizations, resulting in a game where the missions are rigged and consist in little more than finding one of the programmed solutions.

Another genre of games comes from simulation backgrounds; Conway's game of Life or Dymont/Ahl's Hamurabi [1] have

Figure 2: An Autodesk 3DS Max example render using a photorealistic render to showcase the technology's importance in architecture (Source: https://static.chaosgroup.com/gallery_images/images/000/000/159/gallery_image/conor-harll-design-architecture-vray-3ds-max.jpg?1518068742)

inspired generations, The Sims [2] and the Anno series of games are still being continued. These sandbox games typically contain randomly generated open world maps made of grid or block elements, where parametric ruleset govern inter-element relations and operations both during initial creation and during all in-game interactions. The code base, both for behaviour and for visualization, can be very complex, while the data structures for element individualization are kept small to allow for large worlds and massive numbers of players sharing them on a server.

For lack of individual artist design, these games may offer a less naturalistic visual appeal, but much better scalability and extensibility. Minecraft with its Lego esthetics is a prime example and with it carries the ability to become a full parametric CAD design tool, physical experiment simulator or urban planning tool [3] via code extension to the engine and block elements.

Complex buildings like Notre Dame [4] have been replicated and the BlockBy-Block [5] initiative, which uses Minecraft for community driven neighborhood improvement, hints at full digital twins of real-world environments, which even at Minecraft granularity and abstraction wouldn't easily fit our planet on any single computer.

Massive multiplayer games like EVE online [6] feature over 60 000 planets and millions of players inhabiting a single universe. While a lot of the empty space between planets can be fit into a game simulation cube data structure, once players approach a planet's surface or just interact with their spaceships, the level of visual and logical detail to model the parallel universe has no intrinsic limit, only technical barriers. If thousands of players then engage in battle as they did in the "Bloodbath of B-R5RB [7]", the question arises: how does one distribute the model, the interactions and the visualization?

For high-quality lag-less visualization the detailed 3D model should be local to the PC or console to render via the GPU, especially for virtual reality. But where exactly are the other thousands of players moving at rocket speed and where would you aim to hit the enemy? To avoid shooting at ghosts or being killed by an enemy never seen, the detailed logical model of the game universe needs to be kept centrally, updated and perhaps even rendered simultaneously via cloud GPUs, to minimize latency-induced position skew. With the ability to use game engine data for motion prediction to create latency optimized video encoders as fixed function IP blocks on GPUs, the transmission time for GPU generated video content at a given resolution and fidelity now has a manageable, even adjustable upper limit. But the transmission time for a model of

empty space vs. thousands of players and their ships in a single location could vary from milliseconds to way beyond tolerable. Much better than Minecraft granularity, physics at the quality of a car crash simulation, and a game world the size of galaxies make Facebook look rather tiny, and that application runs distributed on millions of servers. Representing space, objects, people and managing their interactions takes more than scaling up an ERP architecture. It requires scale-out and smart partitioning at a level that requires innovating from ground up, implementing a fabric that forwards information by running spatial algebra in hardware on the data plane, not just a spatial operating system [8]. Compared to galaxy sized world models involving immensely complex faster-than-light autonomous vehicles, Pokémon Go's creatures only spawn locally to interact with human players on foot. But it also showcases how games drive this type of innovation towards a global digital twin of everything, the digital replica of our planet that our virtual personal assistants need to link into to work most effectively, to reliably avoid undesired conflicts while encouraging only the interactions we find valuable, which makes it a key topic for EU funded research and open source assets.

The money angle

When it comes to the cost of entertainment, the live performance of a 19th century opera or ballet may top the ranks

Figure 3: Minecraft (Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Minecraft#/media/File:Minecraft_cover.png)

Figure 4: Revenue of music, film and game industry (Source: <https://twitter.com/intangiblecoins/status/1154403586417274880/photo/1>)

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Figure 5: Entertainment cost/hour (Source: <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/multi-billion-dollar-console-gaming-market/>)

of cost per hour: Hundreds of highly skilled professionals are working together to create an ephemeral performance only royal coffers could originally bring to stage. Television added orders of magnitude to the audience cutting the effective cost; recordings and films again offer dramatic cost reductions to being entertained, allowing to vastly expand the stage setting into a full movie with a cast that may count in hundreds, true or now increasingly simulated masses. But gaming replaces the highly skilled and most beautiful (or scary) expensive actors by code, both slashing the cost and adding a degree of interaction, film and television cannot offer. While AIs

are busily being developed to add beauty to average looking actors or drama to uninspired games, we can see how the gaming industry has been eclipsing music and film for more than a decade now, without any sign of slowing down.

And the main reason behind that trend is that the computer automated characters in gaming are even cheaper than the human lay actors in a reality show.

Within the gaming industry we see the cost trend dominating in a similar manner, where the cheapest end-user device, the smartphone every consumer with money

to spend already has, receives the biggest number of low-threshold small-value purchases, which cumulate to a trillion dollar business, leaving PCs and consoles behind.

Entry level smartphones are already as capable as a PlayStation 3, Nintendo Wii or an Xbox 360, while even mid-range smartphones snap at the heels of the PlayStation 4 or Xbox One, which are currently being replaced. But phones, tablets, Chromebooks or pretty much any device with a screen are increasingly used as an end point for remote rendering cloud gaming, which extends the advantage of unbeatable device cost even into the domain of otherwise unaffordable visual experience and has everyone in big tech entering into cloud gaming.

Issues of immaterial possession

Massive gamer populations sharing a single game world is not the only reason cloud-based game rendering has been tried and tried again, starting in 2009 with OnLive [9], purchased by Sony who used the technology for their PlayStation Now offering. More recently practically all web

Figure 6: Gaming revenue by platform with major events (Source: <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/history-of-gaming-by-revenue-share-full-size.html>)

giants have joined the fray, Google with Stadia, Amazon with Luna, Microsoft with xCloud as well as console or hardware vendors like Sony, Nvidia and Apple.

There could be potential consumer benefits, like the ability to play on any screen from mobile phone, tablet, lightweight laptops to the biggest TV or projector screens. Likewise, games can be carried from home to friends, on trips or rides without actually taking disks, consoles or a full gaming rig along. Such a rig can easily cost thousands of Euros, if you want something up-to-date on a PC, consoles still cost hundreds and every few years they become obsolete. If you want to play with your kids or if those come with friends, the multipliers become a challenge.

Blockbuster games not only cost hundreds of millions of real money to develop and are bought by hundreds of millions of gamers, they are also reaching hundreds of gigabytes in size, which

makes casually gaming with several titles seem very attractive in a cloud even with fibre connections. The latest incarnation of Microsoft's flight simulator had many buyers wait days for the first minimal download to complete before they could launch the game and a plane, but the quality is visibly improved from forty years ago.

But one of the biggest concerns with computer games has always been that kids love to share. The earliest Atari home computers and most game consoles started with ROM cartridges for games few kids could copy easily, while taking them to a friend helped spread the ecosystem. When personal computers made it to every desktop with floppy disk, CD and DVD media, their lack of copy protection in the base platforms spawned a copy protection industry, each with its own copy protection scheme, some of which included a rootkit [10]. Popular game consoles from Sega and Sony switched to CD and DVD media for low cost distribution and did include

various technologies [11] to prevent copying disks, while later consoles like Sony's PlayStation and Microsoft Xbox would include cryptographically protected boot ROMs and hypervisors, also very common in mobile phones and now making it into future personal computers [12].

Valve Software started out as a game developer, then started to develop Steam in 2003, originally only as an internet platform to distribute updates for their own games. Since 2009 Valve enabled publishers using their platform to deliver downloaded games encrypted under a user-specific key, which didn't inhibit copying or moving games, but required at least temporary online interactions to enable game start, essentially a DRM so minimally intrusive yet effective it gained market dominance for game distribution mostly by consumer choice. Today it effectively is the app store for personal computer games, it charges the same 30% revenue share Apple and Google demand for their walled gardens, but leads

Figure 7: A cockpit snapshot from Microsoft's 2020 Flight Simulator (Source: Xbox.com)

mostly by customer convenience, allowing users to play games with a maximum of flexibility, local streaming and cloud-based game state replication across machines and even operating systems. That bothers practically everyone at Microsoft and Apple, who would rather prefer complete control over what they consider their own as well as the largest game studios, who would prefer to keep those 30% and have set up similar distribution platforms for their own titles [13] and initiated a price war [14], which may turn out very unfortunate for consumers:

While Steam and the other platforms promote the illusion of a true game purchase, the licence to the game is effectively tied to the platform and lost if it should go down. Competitive pricing would seem to benefit consumers at first glance, but turns platform choice into online gambling

EPIC is using its power as the producer of one of the most important game engines [15] to tilt the platform battle in their favour, much like Microsoft is flexing its Xbox and Windows muscle and Google and Apple work hard to retain their exclusive hold on Android and iOS. This is clearly not in the interest of those consumers, who would prefer to retain and run their purchased games and the non-game applications independent from the distribution platform and across all base architectures supported.

Separating the sale and the rent for the cloud hosting of game distributables and game saves with the right to move both between providers could be a sensible entry point for EU consumer protection regulation.

Nvidia's GeForce NOW is quite different from the other big entrants into the cloud remote gaming market in that it is a pure rental for the hardware. It doesn't include a store but instead validates game licences

against the popular personal computer distribution platforms and ideally works with a cached solid-state copy to reduce game startup times.

Unfortunately, many publishers refuse to let their titles run on GeForce NOW, routinely without comment but evidently not with consumer's best interest at heart.

Google Stadia, Amazon Luna and Microsoft xCloud may offer the same titles you already own for your PC, but not only do you have to purchase them again to run there, you stand to lose them should you terminate your subscription. All of them share that the visual quality, resolution and reactivity is still far below what their marketing materials suggest, while Steam remote gaming in a home LAN proves that it must be a network issue.

True digital goods like e-books or classic audio recordings from Karajan and his Berlin Philharmonics neither suffer decay nor require significant upgrades year after year. They could be inherited for generations and provide enjoyment without any additional expense or revenue. Purchase and ownership by consumers mean far too fickle revenue streams for digital content providers, which surely explains why we see them converging on subscription models for books, music, films, games, Office suites etc. and the delivery of each. The business model for the vendors is so compelling, it is hard to predict how long consumers will retain a choice. And since the reduction of consumer choice provides significant bottom line benefits, addiction is a weapon that chokes itself at every opportunity and requires active countermeasures imposed and controlled via regulation.

One bright thing to look forward to: vendors will still want to sell exclusive shiny hardware to go with that subscription.

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